

1 **Silencing of TLR6 by HPV E6.**

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6 We measured total transcription in cells over-expressing the papillomavirus E6 gene that has described
7 functions in binding and inactivation of p53 for discovery of novel E6 associated cellular functions. We
8 demonstrate here control of *Tlr6* by HPV E6. This was a conserved property of HPV E6 across type: for
9 both HPV16 E6 and for HPV84 E6.

10 Citations

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